

KOPOS criteria set for sustainability and transformation impacts for sustainability initiatives in the food sector

KOPOS working paper

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Summary

This set of criteria can be used to make the sustainability and transformation impacts of sustainability initiatives operating in food systems visible and measurable. The criteria can be used both by the initiatives themselves (as a monitoring tool or for evaluation) and by institutions that want to promote sustainability projects in this area and do not have adequate evaluation criteria available.

1 Introduction

In order to achieve its project objectives, the KOPOS project analyses existing cooperation and pooling approaches that focus their activities on the sustainable development and/or sustainability transformation of food systems. In two model regions (Berlin/Brandenburg & Freiburg), KOPOS has selected a total of 9 pilot projects in a first project phase in order to draw conclusions for the co-creation of **new types of** cooperation approaches, which the project will implement as models in an implementation phase. We were able to identify existing cooperation approaches in both regions by means of analytical steps and located them primarily at the level of so-called **sustainability initiatives**.

Sustainability initiatives work (mostly) at a local level on solutions for global, relevant challenges (e.g. biodiversity loss, mobility, etc.) and are designed, supported and led in a significant way by local actors. They are of crucial importance for the sustainability transformation of society, as they send out impulses over time that change existing unsustainable system structures (Lam et al. 2020¹).

(Local) sustainability initiatives that apply co-operation and pooling as principles of action generally operate in spatially limited social niches and therefore have a limited, measurable ability to effect change at larger scale levels (e.g. regions). Nevertheless - according to the thesis of the KOPOS project - such initiatives develop **a whole series of different effects that are useful for development towards sustainability and/or send out impulses for the transformation of food systems**.

The aim of the criteria set presented here is to record these systematically. The challenges of an applicable criteria set for sustainability-oriented initiatives in food systems are manifold. On the one hand, they must cover the entire thematic breadth in the food sector - from e.g. seed cooperatives to composting projects in allotment gardens; from educational organisations to political initiatives such as food councils. Due to the range of applications mentioned above, the authors decided in favour of developing *criteria* rather than *indicators*. *Criteria* are conditions that must be met in order to achieve a principle that is considered desirable. For example, the dimensions of ecology, economy and social issues can be named if sustainability is defined as a principle to be achieved.

Indicators, on the other hand, are measurable states that can be used to assess whether or not the associated *criteria* are met. In order to increase the applicability of the catalogue of criteria and make it easier to understand, we nevertheless offer possible indicators for each criterion. However, these should be tailored to the specific case study and, if necessary, newly developed.

¹ Lam, D.P.M. et al. 2020. Scaling the impact of sustainability initiatives: a typology of amplification processes. In: Urban Transformation (2020) 2:3.

A further challenge is to develop adequate criteria that describe the effects of transformation.

While a deduction of sustainability criteria via the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is now established, the recording of transformation potential is largely a novelty, which we are approaching with this set of criteria. Transformation refers to processes of social adaptation to global challenges and the associated systemic re-organisation of societal subsystems (such as the energy sector, transport sector or food sector). Processes of societal change are extremely complex and can only be recognised and understood adequately using systemic approaches. As part of the criteria set, we therefore offer a series of proxy criteria that **reflect the potential for a sustainability initiative** to contribute to social transformation. We are aware that local initiatives alone usually do not have sufficient mobilisation potential to change regime structures that support the current agri-food system. System transformations are non-linear, lengthy, involve and affect a large number of actors and therefore largely resist the possibility of centralised planning and control. Therefore, the criteria rather depict possible transformation paths to a more sustainable food system that sustainability initiatives can take.

In total, two dimensions are mapped in the criteria set:

- On the one hand, potentials from an actual state of a sustainability initiative can be mapped, which is particularly suitable for an ex-ante analysis. This primarily concerns the recording of the potential for contributing to a sustainability transformation.
- On the other hand, the effects of a sustainability initiative can be mapped, which is particularly useful for an ex-post analysis.

For whom are these criteria useful? We see two main areas of application and target groups: Firstly, the set of criteria can be used by sustainability initiatives themselves to document various sustainability impacts. Selected criteria can be used for monitoring and for measuring success. It could also be used for external communication. True to the motto: 'Do good and talk about it', the criteria serve to underpin the abstract goal of sustainability with concrete impact dimensions. Ultimately, they also serve to increase the recognition of sustainability-promoting activities.

Secondly, we see potential funding providers as a second user group. In some cases, they are faced with the challenge of translating abstractly formulated funding policy objectives (e.g. sustainability of food systems) into criteria worthy of funding that are subsequently measurable and comprehensible. If "sustainability transformation" is formulated even more strongly as a political goal in the future, there will be a need to record transformation effects more than before. We also want to address this (anticipated) need with our criteria.

2 Brief derivation of the criteria set

The logic of the criteria set is essentially based on the assessment framework of the study "*Criteria for assessing the transformation potential of sustainability initiatives*"², which the Ecologic Institute prepared on behalf of the German Federal Environment Agency (UBA) in 2019. It presents a system for recording and assessing the sustainability and transformation potential of civil society activities in order to disclose the value and transformation potential of these initiatives along all sustainability dimensions and to create a basis for political recognition and support. For the development of the assessment categories and criteria, numerous scientific papers and 14 existing assessment and criteria systems were analysed, including the **UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** and their applicability to civil society sustainability initiatives.

As the KOPOS project pursued comparable goals with its "pilot projects" and "model projects"³, an adaptation of the framework seemed functional. The KOPOS consortium essentially extended the user group of the impact indicators to **all** forms of organisation (not just civil society actors) and also focused more strongly on the topic of "regional agri-food systems", whereas the UBA study did not specify a thematic focus.

Roughly speaking, the framework of the UBA study derives **key questions from sustainability and transformation criteria**, which in turn are derived from common indicator sets (e.g. SDGs, sustainability indicators of the German government, etc.). This initially results in two dimensions - "sustainability impacts" and "transformation potential" - which are summarised into a common framework (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Criteria for assessing sustainability and transformation potential
(original source: Wunder et al. 2019:66)

² Wunder, S.; Albrecht, S.; Porsch, L.; Öhler, L. 2019. Kriterien zur Bewertung des Transformationspotentials von Nachhaltigkeitsinitiativen. Umweltbundesamt Texte 22/2019.

³ The selection of "pilot projects" and "model projects" is a core characteristic of the methodological approach of the KOPOS project. More information can be found at <https://kopos-projekt.de>

The study by Wunder et al. (2019) also considered other assessment categories that are assumed to be essential prerequisites for sustainability initiatives to be effective in terms of sustainability and transformation. The two additional categories are "**organisational capacity to act**" and "**scalability**". They are described as optional categories in the UBA study, which can be used separately from the sustainability assessment.

As part of the criteria development in KOPOS, the framework of the study by Wunder et al. (2019) was largely adopted (in particular the dimensions "transformation potential", "sustainability", "organisational capacity to act" and "scalability"), but adapted thematically to regional agri-food systems and to the target group of the KOPOS pilot projects (or the sustainability initiatives).

Figure 2: Overall criteria framework for sustainability assessment
(Origin: Wunder et al. 2019:67)

Adjustments compared to the study by Wunder et al. (2019) and new developments relate in particular to

- the indicators in the **sustainability dimension "Economy"**, where the KOPOS consortium has now focused more strongly on the evaluation framework of "Richtig rechnen"⁴ ([link](#)), an indicator set that was co-developed for agricultural businesses by the research organisation "die Agronauten". The reason for the stronger focus on

⁴ Beckmann, J.; Hiß, C.; Hiß, M.; Strauß, K.; Gasser, A.; Herzig, C.; Jakob, M. 2019. "Richtig Rechnen in der Landwirtschaft: Durchführung einer erweiterten Finanzbuchhaltung unter Einbeziehung der monetären Bewertung externer Effekte". Final report on the research project. November 2019. URL: <https://www.agronauten.net/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/Projektbericht-Richtig-Rechnen.pdf> (accessed: 25 April 2022)

economic criteria was that the accompanied sustainability initiatives are more business/commercial activities and not exclusively volunteer-based,

- a **shift in focus** from a pure survey of potential in the **direction of a impact assessment of sustainable and transformational practices** that implement sustainability initiatives in food sectors,
- an **expansion of the potential user group** of the criteria set from so far primarily civil society actors to public and market actors, or "hybrid" forms of organisation that bring together actors from different sectors,
- a **more precise alignment of the criteria with the two topics of the fields of action** of KOPOS⁵, but without excluding other agri-food topics per se (e.g. circular systems, dietary change),
- emphasising the **spatial context of KOPOS** in the sense of urban-rural cooperation and
- contributions for "**culturally determined sustainability values**".

⁵ This refers to the two topic areas "Short value chains" and "Access to and securing land".

3 Presentation of the criteria set with possible indicators

Dimension	Top category	Subcategory	Criterion	Explanation	Possible indicators (with unit)
Organisational prerequisites	Internal organisation of sustainability initiatives		Common values, goals and expectations	It is important for a sustainability initiative to establish a common vision and common goals. A point of reference for the recording of common goals can be documents from the founding of the initiative and their largely standardized presentation of the self-image on websites, in discussions with participants, etc. The mere fact that there are common (meaningful) documents suggests there are common goals that have been agreed upon. Established discussion processes and strategy meetings within the initiative can also be indicators that common goals have been agreed upon and are continuously reflected upon.	Published documents that state values, objectives and expectations (yes/no) Strategy discussions/meetings held with members/participants (yes/no)
			External networking	A deep and broad external network increases access to resources and broader support. This allows the initiative to be more compatible with existing solutions and resistance can be uncovered at an early stage. The needs and experiences of other groups can also be utilised and taken up by the initiative. Political influence and thus greater attention and potential dissemination can be achieved, for example, by involving the initiative in political activities or lobbying. Recognising external parties, especially influential multipliers, supports its dissemination.	Number of active members in the initiative (total) Direct, personal contacts to the local political level (mayor, parties) (yes/no) Direct, personal contacts with influential civil society organisations and regional networks (yes/no) Amount of followers in social media channels (total)

	Scalability		Comprehensibility/ Connectivity	<p>The comprehensibility of an approach increases the likelihood of public acceptance. The initiative can contribute to comprehensibility by communicating its goals and approaches clearly and comprehensibly depending on the target group and by managing expectations. The ability to connect with existing everyday practices and the specific local context is also conducive to communication, acceptance and the likelihood of implementation (e.g. if existing regional meeting points or existing routines are utilised by people, an existing need is addressed, etc.). Radical innovations (which, for example, involve a major restructuring of the daily procedures or routines or require a high initial investment in relationships, processes, necessary infrastructure, etc.) are more likely to meet with resistance. In the latter case, the initiative should be prepared to deal with this and utilise it (for example, by providing infrastructure, communication channels, services, etc.) in order to further develop the innovation.</p>	<p>Availability of communication media for direct contact with interested parties (e.g. flyers, website, explanatory videos, social media, visualisations) (yes/no)</p> <p>Presence of brands and symbols with recognition potential in external communication (yes/no)</p> <p>Existence of press reports on the initiative and its objectives, products and values (yes/no)</p> <p>Inclusion of the idea or initiative as "best practice" in policy or strategy papers of politicians and associations (yes/no)</p> <p>Invitations to events to present the idea or initiative (yes/no)</p>
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Dimension	Top category	Subcategory	Criterion	Explanation	Possible indicators (with unit)
Transformation potential	Initiating social debates		Visibility and experiencability of alternative approaches	Sustainability initiatives can bring alternative approaches to life, "set an example", test them in "real-world laboratories", inspire or irritate and can thus stimulate a change of perspective and dialogue. Initiatives that make transformative practices visible, tangible and experienceable increase the potential for transformation, as learning processes for more sustainability are stimulated by linking them to concrete experiences.	<p>Existence of open, participative formats (e.g. transparent manufactory, participatory action, tastings, guided tours, etc.) (yes/no)</p> <p>Number of participants in open and participatory formats (total)</p> <p>Opportunities for participation/co-determination by third parties (membership, partners, shareholders, etc.) (yes/no)</p>
	Profound innovations		New solutions for profound change	<p>This refers to innovations that are applied, developed and tested by the initiatives. We understand innovations to be changes that are the result of social processes, such as a new guiding principle, a new practice, a new product or a new process and thus influence the direction of social developments. These can be technical innovations, new business models, new forms of co-operation or new consumption styles. They are also themselves embedded in social practices and contexts, and if the niche-shaped new social practices stabilise and spread, they change and transform social conditions.</p> <p>Innovations that are also geared towards the sustainable development of society (in the sense of a social transformation) link the innovations with ambitious sustainability goals. The innovation must be evaluated in the respective spatial and thematic context (absolutely or relatively new guiding idea, new practice, product or process for a profound change in lifestyles, practices, services, technologies & demonstration of sustainable alternatives).</p>	<p>Describing or writing down the novelty value of the sustainability initiative in documents/website etc. (yes/no)</p> <p>Presence of references to sustainability goals in documents of the initiative (yes/no)</p> <p>Existence of documents and/or documented events that address the state of existing unsustainable practices (yes/no)</p> <p>Membership of the initiative in political networks that address sustainability (e.g. attac, Farmers for Future, food council etc.) (yes/no)</p>

				It can also be an innovation that destabilises existing non-sustainable practices (e.g. through niche approaches or through questioning and public discussion).	
Linking sustainability dimensions		Consideration of undesirable consequences	An important characteristic of transformative initiatives is the assessment or awareness of the possible consequences of one's own actions and whether undesirable side effects may arise, so that an innovation in one sector/area may bring significant improvements, but at the expense of other relevant sectors. These include, for example, economic effects at the expense of social and ecological sustainability, but also issues of spatial justice (e.g. positive effects in a small urban area vs. negative effects for those living in the surrounding urban area).	<p>Existence of (external) advisory bodies in the initiatives (yes/no)</p> <p>Existence of an analysis to assess different aspects of impact (yes/no)</p> <p>Existence of consultations or hearings in strategic decision-making processes of initiatives (yes/no)</p> <p>Existence of discussion formats with citizens and (other) practitioners for an overall view of the expected impacts (yes/no)</p>	
Changes in everyday practice		Access to rooms, infrastructure and products	Sustainable action is closely linked to the existence of suitable structures that make sustainable action possible in the first place. In this context, we can speak of infrastructures for changing everyday practices. These can be spaces that are used for meetings, access to educational programmes, access to products (e.g. market structures), etc. These infrastructures make it possible to try out alternative (everyday) practices.	<p>Secured availability of spaces for changing everyday practices (e.g. meeting rooms, markets, etc.) (yes/no)</p> <p>Assured availability of infrastructure for changing everyday practices (e.g. storage capacity, kitchens, water, electricity, etc.)</p>	

					Availability of marketable products and/or services (yes/no)
	Diet and food culture	Eating and dietary culture that includes sustainable dietary practices	<p>Dietary practices and the characteristics of certain food and eating cultures are shaped by numerous factors and in turn influence the sustainability balance of diets. The extent of the need for transformation of the food system will therefore inevitably lead to a change in eating and food cultures. In addition to changes in the consumption of certain products (e.g. (regional) origin, animal/plant composition, degree of processing, etc.) and changes in production and processing methods (e.g. artisanal/traditional), other aspects also play a role: changes in routines, skills, competences, the degree of interaction, the duration and frequency of shared meals (commensality), eating as part of ceremonies and cultural identification, table manners, etc.</p> <p>How these changes can be assessed from a sustainability and transformation perspective can and must be determined using the respective criteria anchored there. However, a change in the "overall structure" of the eating and dietary culture(s) can provide a helpful indication of the depth of the transformation and the establishment of "new norms and routines".</p>	Description of the key characteristics in relation to a changed food culture as a whole	

Dimension	Top category	Subcategory	Criterion	Explanation	Possible indicators (with unit)
Sustainability	Ecology	Biodiversity	Product and variety diversity	Biodiversity can cover various aspects. One aspect that includes biodiversity in the production of food is the utilisation of crop varieties used. This can include variability within a species as well as different types of crops within an agricultural or cultivation system. Activities to improve biodiversity can be carried out directly by farmers and indirectly by non-farmers through activities along the value chain that support the improvement of biodiversity on agricultural land.	Number of different crops per area Number of crop rotation elements on the farm (total) Number of different varieties (e.g. regional variety, old variety) of a crop (e.g. different carrot varieties)
			Diversity of land use	The maintenance and/or creation of near-natural landscape elements in agricultural production systems supports, in particular, the biodiversity of flora and fauna. Near-natural elements can include hedges, windbreaks, bodies of water or riparian strips. Ecologically valuable agricultural systems such as paludiculture and measures temporarily integrated into agricultural systems (such as agroforestry, lark windows, flower strips, etc.) also have positive effects on biodiversity.	Type and area of annual and perennial, e.g. flower strips, fallow land, agroforestry, (descriptive, quantitative) Proportion of area of semi-natural landscape elements in the total farm area (in %)
		Soil	Prevention of soil compaction and sealing	Preventing soil compaction, which is mainly caused by tilling with agricultural machinery at the wrong time, has significant effects on soil organisms and (generally) on soil health (e.g. water permeability, air and nutrient exchange, etc.). Reduced tillage and consideration of the moisture-related risk of compaction, e.g. through lower axle loads of the agricultural machinery used, can prevent compaction.	Total tractor weight (agricultural machine plus trailer) on a field (tonnes per acre) Number of passes/ growing season and field (of which in unfavourable soil moisture conditions)

		<p>With regard to the issue of securing land, the increase in fully or partially sealed areas due to infrastructure and settlement expansion plays a particularly important role. Agricultural land in the so-called outskirts of settlements is particularly at risk of being re-zoned for non-agricultural purposes, as the legislator particularly supports building on the outskirts of villages.</p>	<p>Assessment of the soil fertility status (e.g. spade diagnosis, aggregate condition; root penetration; earthworm burrows/presence of earthworms, etc.) (improvement/deterioration: none, slight, medium, significant)</p> <p>Area saved from (partial) sealing (square metres or hectares)</p>
	Prevention of Soil erosion	<p>To maintain soil functions, it is important to avoid pollutant inputs, erosion, sealing, compaction (e.g. by large machines) and the loss of soil organisms and the humus layer.</p> <p>Soil erosion is mainly caused by wind and water, whereby the topsoil is removed and is no longer available for agricultural production. Farmers can make agricultural systems more resilient to erosion by, for example, ploughing soil as little and as gently as possible or by ensuring permanent green cover (e.g. mulching), which prevents topsoil from drying out quickly. Measures to protect against wind erosion can also include the creation of near-natural landscape elements (in particular hedges, windbreaks and agroforestry systems).</p>	<p>Green cover (proportion of days per year)</p> <p>Type and frequency of tillage (descriptive)</p> <p>Types and area of creation/maintenance of near-natural landscape elements (descriptive / area in ha)</p>
Climate	Climate adaptation and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in agriculture	<p>In agriculture, large quantities of greenhouse gases can be saved by closing nutrient cycles, through area-adapted animal husbandry or by reducing the consumption of mainly synthetic nitrogen fertilisers (e.g. in organic farming, legumes as a preceding crop, farm manure instead of mineral fertilisers, etc.), diesel (reduced tillage, etc.).</p>	<p>Use of synthetic fertilisers (kg/ha/a)</p> <p>Total fuel consumption (l/a)</p> <p>Proportion of farm manure in total fertiliser use (in %)</p> <p>Livestock units (quantity/ha)</p>

		Measures to increase yields through breeding, changes in farming practices, etc. also contribute to improving the carbon footprint and the use of resources.	
	Reduction of greenhouse gases in the value chain	There are various ways to save CO ₂ along the value chain. These include short distances in regional recycling systems and resource-saving logistics concepts. GHGs can also be saved through efficient storage concepts (pooling) and infrastructures and measures to reduce food losses and waste. There is further potential in processing food that is as fresh and unprocessed as possible, as it undergoes few resource-consuming processing steps and has low or no emissions from cooling/storage. The economical (or even recyclable) use of packaging materials also saves resources and reduces GHG emissions. Finally, a food system that focuses more on plant-based diets (e.g. in the context of communal catering) is one of the most effective measures for reducing GHGs in the value chain.	<p>Energy consumption for storage per tonne of goods (in kWh)</p> <p>Proportion of unpackaged food in the goods produced (in %)</p> <p>Proportion of unpackaged food in the goods sold (in %)</p> <p>Proportion of food losses and waste (in %)</p> <p>Saved utilisation of animal products/use of conversion measures (e.g. in communal catering) (descriptive))</p>
	Utilisation of regenerative energy sources	The production of renewable energies (bioenergy etc.) including self-generated electricity (photovoltaics, wind) reduces CO ₂ emissions and can thus contribute to climate protection, if used in the long run. In contrast to fossil resources, energy sources from biomass only release the amount of the greenhouse gas carbon dioxide (CO ₂) during combustion (or other conversion) that the plants have previously removed from the atmosphere during growth. However, the energy required to cultivate and convert the biomass must be taken into account. Irrespective of this, bioenergy sources emit less CO ₂ in their overall balance than oil, coal and natural gas.	<p>Type of renewable energy generated and amount of electricity from own sources (kWh per year)</p> <p>Share of renewable self-generated electricity in total electricity consumption (in %)</p>

			Carbon sequestration (humus, green planting)	The type of agricultural land use can also reduce GHG emissions and even act as a carbon sink (carbon farming), binding carbon from the air in the soil. This can be supported by various methods, such as soil-conserving cultivation methods to build up humus, improved crop rotations to regenerate the arable soil, the cultivation of plant varieties with strong root penetration, the cultivation and use of undersown crops, the introduction and expansion of agroforestry and the storage of carbon, e.g. by incorporating biochar into the soil.	Number of crop rotation elements (total) or multi-element crop rotations (yes/no) Type and method of soil cultivation (descriptive) Carbon stock in (top) soil (tons/ha)
		Water	Water consumption	Water-saving irrigation practices in agriculture are of great importance for sustainability. This applies in particular to regions where groundwater levels are falling due to climate change and high water consumption in other sectors. There is also various potential for water-saving action along the value chain. These include water-saving concepts in the processing of food (e.g. reduced use of water for washing).	Water consumed (hl/a)
	Economy	Economic ability to act	Economic efficiency	Economic efficiency refers to the ability of an institution to operate sustainably in a business sense, thus increasing its resilience to external shocks. An institution is economically viable if it not only covers its costs, but is also able to build up investment capacity. Important areas of economic viability include financial resources, personnel and the availability of operating resources.	Income/expenditure balance sheet (in Euro / a) Liquidity (in Euro)

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Employment	<p>Employment refers to the ability of sustainability initiatives to generate jobs that are adequate, fair and appropriate. Here, employment relationships subject to social insurance contributions with collectively agreed wages should be seen as positive in the sense of a "positive" employment structure. Not included in this category are opportunities for unpaid employment provided by volunteers and/or family members.</p>	<p>Number of employees ("socially insured") (total full-time equivalents)</p> <p>Number of trainees (total)</p>
Sales of regionally produced products	<p>The turnover of regionally produced products is one aspect of regional value creation processes that is seen as positive for the establishment of regional production and consumption systems. This criterion is relevant for producers of products and services who market and sell their goods within regional borders. As there is no universal definition of regionality, "region" is defined as an area that should generally be located between a local/municipal and a state level. However, as regionality is not oriented towards administrative boundaries alone, the definition of regions is very fluid. Regionality is therefore often equated with "short" distribution channels to the consumer or to the next link in the value chain (processors, retailers, etc.).</p>	<p>Total turnover of regionally marketed products (in euros/year)</p> <p>Share of regionally marketed products in total production (in %)</p>
Purchase of regionally produced/manufactured products	<p>The purchase of regionally produced or manufactured products is one aspect of mapping regional value creation processes. It is primarily (but not exclusively) relevant for actors in the value chain that follow the production of food (i.e. processors, distribution and marketing).</p>	<p>Share of sales of regional goods in total sales (in %)</p>

			Measures to minimise pre- and post-harvest losses in the value chain	<p>Food losses along the agricultural value chain occur at all levels of the value chain and have a negative impact on producers of regional foodstuffs, as they are unable to market their goods, which in turn weakens their economic capacity to act. Measures to reduce food losses can be taken at different points in the value chain and range from concepts for processing of (previously) non-marketable food to medium and long-term guarantees for purchase quantities and measures to reduce wasted food.</p>	<p>Estimated post-harvest losses of food products (in %)</p> <p>Turnover of food from B- and C-grade produce (in euros)</p>
Social affairs	Health (in connection with diet)	Production and distribution of fresh, regional food	<p>Not taking into account the health of agricultural soils and ecosystems, the focus here is on nutrition-related human health. A balanced diet with fresh, minimally processed, mainly plant-based foods is part of a healthy diet that contributes to or supports physical well-being. Sustainability-oriented initiatives often help to produce these foods or make them available and accessible by creating a basis for healthy food production, producing diverse, low-pollutant, regional products from agricultural produce and realising low-nutrient-loss processing of the food and distribution to consumers.</p>	<p>Quantity of low/unprocessed food produced (in tonnes per year)</p> <p>Contribution to the provision of plant-based catering options (according to "Planetary Health Diet", according to „Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ernährung e.V.“ etc.) (descriptive)</p> <p>Increase accessibility to fresh, minimally processed, primarily plant-based foods (subscription boxes, community supply, cooperation with retail chains, market offers, etc.) (descriptive)</p>	
	Social justice	Anti-discrimination	<p>Social justice refers to equal opportunities for people to be able to take advantage of society's offers and services without discrimination, regardless of gender identity, age, origin, religion, disability or economic status. This includes, among other things, whether the sustainability initiative contributes to reducing discrimination and promoting inclusion, as well as facilitating solidarity.</p>	<p>Equal pay for men and women in the initiative (yes/no)</p> <p>Remuneration of employees according to collective agreements (yes/no)</p>	

				Measures against discrimination can, for example, address gender inequality (e.g. gender parity, gender pay gap) in employment relationships or enable or at least facilitate access to healthy food for all population groups (in particular also underprivileged social classes) (e.g. through „Volxküchen" or population kitchens, free catering offers or solidarity-based payment models for food).	Ratio of men to women in decision-making bodies of the initiative (X:Y) Number of inclusive workplaces (total) Measures for access to healthy food for all (especially for underprivileged population groups) (descriptive)
			Educational offers	Access and the right to (dietary) education for all are at the centre of the criterion of educational opportunities. Education for sustainability is one of the key leverage points for initiating a sustainability transformation in society. Sustainability initiatives that integrate educational programmes into their activities therefore make a valuable contribution to people's learning about sustainability. Educational programmes can address all age groups and range from one-time to serial, from digital to physical offers.	Type of educational programme (descriptive) Participants in educational programmes (total /a)